

LEARNING EXPERIENCE OF BIG FARMERS IN SUGARCANE CULTIVATION

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Abstract:

The effective learning experience can be had effective learning situations provided by a skillful instructor who knows what he wants, who has the materials to accomplish his goals and the skills to use them effectively. The study was conducted in Cuddalore district of Tamil Nadu. A total number of ten sugarcane technologies with technical units were selected for the study. The result of the study Big farmers possessed high level of learning experience. The learning experience may be further enhanced by majority of the Big farmers to prefer personal localite and personal cosmopolite channels for getting information.

Introduction:

The key to agricultural development lies in the mind, heart and hands of the farmers. Communication of agricultural information was inefficient and ineffective leading to an increase in the gap between innovations in the lab and the adoption in the fields by the farmers. Thus, there is need to have more effective transfer of technology system. Realizing the gap in research and accumulated felt needs at the grass root level, the present investigation was formulated as an attempt to study the following objectives

- ✓ Relationship of socio - economics and psychological characteristics with the learning experience of Big farmers.
- ✓ To study the practice wise learning experience of Big farmers in sugarcane cultivation

Methodology:

The study was carried out in selected six villages from six blocks of Cuddalore district of Tamil Nadu. A total number of ten sugarcane technologies with technological units were selected for the study. The eighty respondent were selected from six villages using proportionate random sampling. Fourteen independent variables were selected based on judges opinion. Data collection was done through a well constructed and pre tested interview schedule collected data were analysed by using appropriate statistical tests.

Findings and Discussion:

The zero order correlation coefficient (r) was worked out to study the relationship of independent variables with the learning experience of Big sugarcane cultivators and the results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Relationship of socio - economic and psychological characteristics with the learning experience level of sugarcane cultivators

S.No	Variables	V value
		Big fanners (n = 80)
X ₁	Age	-0.058 NS
X ₂	Educational status	0.098 NS
X ₃	Occupational status	0.911 NS
X ₄	Area under cultivation	0.014 NS
X ₅	Farming experience	0.046 NS
X ₆	Experience in sugarcane	-0.046 NS
X ₇	Annual income	0.241*
X ₈	Social participation	-0.207 NS
X ₉	Extension agency contact	0.616**
X ₁₀	Decision making	-0.198 NS
X ₁₁	Mass media exposure	0.489**
X ₁₂	Scientific orientation	-0.0021 NS
X ₁₃	Information source utilization	0.485**
X ₁₄	Innovativeness	0.054 NS

* - Significant at 5% level
 ** - Significant at 5% level
 NS - Non - significant at 5% level

In could be seen from the table 1 that out of fourteen independent variables, only four variable viz., Annual income(X₇) Extension agency contact(X₉) Information source utilization (X₁₃) and mass media (X₁₁) were found to have positive and highly significant relationship with the leading experience of Big categories sugarcane growers. The extension agency contact, mass media exposure and information source utilization might have provided the opportunity for the farmers to contact authenticates sources of information to learn. This might

have resulted in higher learning experience. Similar finding was also reported by Athimuthu (1990).

Practice Wise Learning Experience of Big Farmers:

The state collected on the recommend practices learn by the Big farmers through the learning activities under the personal locality, personal cosmopolite and mass media channels are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Practice wise learning experience of Big farmers in sugarcane

S.No	Technology	Learning Activities					
		Personal Localite		Personal		Mask Media	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
1	Sett relation	67	83.75	31	38.75	21	26.25
2	Sett treatment	30	37.50	51	63.75	33	41.25
3	Planting	64	80.00	25	31.25	17	21.25
4	Herbicide application	29	36.25	47	58.75	21	26.25
5	Bio-fertilizer application	55	68.75	33	41.25	20	25.00
6	Phosphatic fertilizer	77	96.25	16	20.00	14	23.75
7	Nitrogenous fertilizer	74	92.50	18	22.50	25	31.25
8	Potash fertilize	70	87.50	15	18.75	19	23.75
9	Control early short borer	48	60.00	41	51.25	28	28.75
10	Bio-control agent for inter-node borer	27	33.75	45	56.25	30	37.50

* Multiple Response

From table 2, it could be observed that majority of the Big farmers performed the learning activities under personal localite channels learning of nine practices viz., sett selection (83.75 per cent), planting (80.00 per cent), bio fertilizer application (68.75 per cent), phosphotic fertilizer application (96.25 per cent), nitrogenous fertilizer application (92.50 per cent) and potash fertilizer application (87.50per cent). The learning activities under personal cosmopolite channels were utilized by majority of the farmers (60.00% per cent) for one practice namely, herbicide application.

It could be inferred that the Big farmers performed the learning activities under personal localite channels in their learning for most of the practices. It might be due to easy accessible, approaches and cost - effective nature of personal localite channels. The extension agency contact, mass media exposure and information source utilization might have provided the opportunity for the farmers to contact authenticated sources of information to learn. This might have resulted in higher learning experience. The same trend was reported by Mahendra pandian(1992).

Conclusion:

In this light of the present investigation, it can be concluded that only three characteristic like extension agency contact, information sources utilization and innovativeness have significant and positive relationship with learning experience. The majority of the Big farmers to prefer personal localite channels for getting information due to easy approachable, accessible and cost effective nature of personal localite channels this might be have enabled the Big farmers to use them frequently. Hence it is necessary to identity the extension educational programmes such as trainings, discussion meetings, demonstration and field visit etc., for need perceptual changes among the sugarcane cultivators.

References:

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